

A FINITE ELEMENT MODEL FOR DISCONTINUOUS AND RANDOMLY-ORIENTED STRAND THERMOPLASTIC CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Discontinuous and randomly oriented chopped tape thermoplastic CFRP (CTT) classified as ROS (Randomly Oriented Strands) has high mechanical properties in in-plane direction and lower in out-of-plane direction. In order to predict the deformation behavior of CTT, a constitutive model considering in-plane and out-of-plane anisotropy is necessary. The objective of this study is to propose a simple finite element (FE) model, defining in-plane homogeneity, out-of-plane anisotropy, strain hardening and damage initiation/propagation without consideration of the shape of the tapes explicitly. The parameters of FE model were obtained by in-plane and out-of-plane test. The criteria of damage initiation were identified from tensile test. The damage propagation was defined as non-linear curve obtained from the out-of-plane shear property. As the results of FE analysis using the identified damage criteria, the mechanical flexural behavior and the distribution of damage agreed well with experimental results for a variety of specimen.

1 INTRODUCTION

In automotive industry, automobile weight reduction is required for improving fuel efficiency. CFRP has been applied to vehicle component in substitution for metal.

We have developed randomly oriented chopped tape thermoplastic CFRP (CTT) classified as ROS (Randomly Oriented Strands) composites [1]. The schematic image of CTT is shown in Figure 1. The chopped tapes were reinforced by unidirectional carbon fibers and impregnated with thermoplastic resins. CTT consists of stacked sheet of in-plane randomly oriented chopped tapes. CTT has the characteristic of high processability due to discontinuity of fiber. In order to apply CTT to a variety of structural elements of automobiles, a constitute model of this material is highly demanded to predict deformation behavior. In particular, it is important to predict flexural behavior for effective design of structural component.

In one of the previous researches on the constitutive models for ROS composites, Selezneva et al. analyzed the tensile behavior considering fracture paths on the strands interface [2]. This model needs the explicit strands shape. Therefore, this model is not practical due to significantly high calculation cost when applying it to complicated structural components.

In this study, we propose a simple model defining in-plane homogeneity and out-of-plane anisotropy without consideration of the shape of the strands of tapes explicitly. Our model is available in general finite element software with low calculation cost. The results of flexural stress-strain

relationship and its damage propagation of the proposed model were compared with the experimental results.

Figure 1: Schematic image of CTT.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

CTT consisted of carbon fiber (TR50S, MITSUBISHI CHEMICAL) and acid-modified polypropylene (PP, TOYOBO). Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio values were 240 GPa and 0.2 for carbon fiber, and for PP, 1.80 GPa and 0.3. The volume fraction of carbon fiber was 50 % in the unidirectional chopped tapes. The size of strand was 35 mm in length, 15 mm in width and 0.1 mm in thickness. The test specimens were made by compression moulding after stacked in-plane randomly oriented strands into a shape of sheet.

2.2 Methods

We carried out tensile and in-plane shear test in order to obtain in-plane material parameters in the proposed FE model. Out-of-plane properties for the model were evaluated by out-of-plane shear test. To validate the model, we also carried out three-point bending test.

2.2.1 Evaluation of the in-plane properties for FE model

For evaluation of the in-plane tensile modulus E_{11} and yield stress σ_{11}^y , the tensile test was performed referring to JIS K 7164. The test was conducted at crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min. The shape of specimen was rectangle with the length 250 mm, width of 25 mm and thickness of 2 mm. The gauge length was 100 mm. Figure 2 shows the stress-strain curve of the tensile test. The stress-strain curve was obtained as almost linear and showed brittle fracture at tensile strain of 0.01036. At the fracture point, plastic tensile strain ε_{11}^p was $3.3e-4$. The tensile modulus was evaluated at linear region on the stress-strain curve. The tensile yield stress was determined as intersection of linear elasticity and the stress-strain curve. The values of E_{11} and σ_{11}^y were 32,300 MPa and 238 MPa respectively.

For evaluation of the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} and yield stress σ_{12}^y , the in-plane shear test method was employed referring to ASTM D7078 at crosshead speed 2.0 mm/min [3]. In-plane shear strain was obtained from bi-axial strain gauge on the central of test specimen. From the test results as Figure 3 shows for instance, the stress-strain relationship showed that the fracture behavior was brittle. The in-plane shear modulus and yield stress were estimated in the same way as the in-plane tensile ones. The values G_{12} and σ_{12}^y were 12,100 MPa and 72.3 MPa respectively.

Figure 2: Tensile stress-tensile strain curve of tensile test.

Figure 3: Relationship between in-plane shear stress and in-plane shear strain.

2.2.2 Evaluation the out-of-plane properties for FE model

For obtaining the out-of-plane shear properties, Matsuo et al. have proposed a new test specimen based on double notch compression test method (JIS K 7092) [4]. Figure 4 shows the proposed test specimen. The compressive speed was 0.5 mm/min. The notch depth of the test specimen was deeper than the standard one. The out-of-plane shear strain was obtained from bi-axial strain gauge on the center of test specimen. The stress-strain curve showed nonlinearity as a solid line shown in Figure 5. This result reflected the out-of-plane property of CTT were dominated by matrix’s elasto-plastic property. The out-of-plane shear modulus G_{31} and yield stress σ_{31}^y were estimated in the same way as the in-plane properties. The values G_{31} and σ_{31}^y were 1,600 MPa and 13.7 MPa respectively.

Figure 4: The proposed test specimen for out-of-plane shear test.

Figure 5: Out-of-plane shear stress-out-of-plane shear strain curve.

2.2.3 Three-point bending test for validation of FE model

The three-point bending test was performed referring to JIS K 7074 at stroke speed 0.1 min^{-1} . The shape of the bending test specimen was rectangle with the length of 100 mm, the width of 60 mm. The thickness of specimen was 2, 4 and 6 mm. The distance between supports was 80 mm.

3 FE MODEL

We utilized FEM solver Abaqus/Standard 2018. Three dimensional 8 node continuum element (C3D8) was used. The constitutive behaviors in the FE model consist of four components:

1) linear elasticity, 2) yield function, 3) strain hardening and 4) damage initiation/propagation.

1) The elastic moduli obtained from the test results were employed to the anisotropic linear elastic parameters. The values of Poisson's ratio were calculated from rule of mixtures. The material model assumed that CTT has in-plane homogeneity and out-of-plane anisotropy, because the tapes in CTT were randomly oriented in the in-plane direction and stacked in the out-of-plane direction. Anisotropic linear elastic parameters are summarized in Table 1 [1]. Material directions are shown in Figure 1.

$E_{11} = E_{22}$ (MPa)	E_{33} (MPa)	G_{12} (MPa)	$G_{23} = G_{31}$ (MPa)	ν_{12} (-)	$\nu_{23} = \nu_{31}$ (-)
32,300	5,290	12,100	1,600	0.332	0.245

Table 1: Anisotropic linear elastic parameters.

2) Hill's yield function of Equation (1) was used to consider for anisotropic yield behavior. From associated flow rule, the equivalent plastic strain increment for Hill's yield criterion was defined by Equation (2) [5, 6]. Hill's yield parameters are shown in Table 2 [1]. These parameters were calculated from yield stress of test results.

$$F(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + G(\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2 + H(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 2L\sigma_{23}^2 + 2M\sigma_{31}^2 + 2N\sigma_{12}^2 = \bar{\sigma}^2 \quad (1)$$

$$d\bar{\varepsilon}^p = \sqrt{\frac{F(d\varepsilon_{11}^p)^2 + G(d\varepsilon_{22}^p)^2 + H(d\varepsilon_{33}^p)^2}{FG + FH + GH} + \frac{2(d\varepsilon_{23}^p)^2}{L} + \frac{2(d\varepsilon_{31}^p)^2}{M} + \frac{2(d\varepsilon_{12}^p)^2}{N}} \quad (2)$$

Where $\bar{\sigma}$: equivalent stress, σ_{ij} : stress component ($i, j = 1\sim 3$), $d\bar{\varepsilon}^p$: equivalent plastic strain increment, $d\varepsilon_{ij}^p$: plastic strain increment component ($i, j = 1\sim 3$), F , G , H , L , M , N : material constant.

$F = G$	H	$L = M$	N
9.92e-3	8.13e-5	1.50	5.42e-2

Table 2: Hill's yield function parameters.

3) Stress-strain curve from out-of-plane shear test was used as strain hardening curve after yielding. Figure 6 shows strain hardening curve of the FE model.

Figure 6: Strain hardening curve.

4) Stress triaxiality η was used for controlling damage initiation criteria. If stress triaxiality is negative, it indicates compression damage. Conversely, positive stress triaxiality indicates tensile damage. Indeed, tape delamination occurred firstly in the compression side of the specimen from in-situ X-ray CT observations during the flexural test [7]. Thus the criteria for damage initiation strain was determined $1.0e-4$ at compression side ($\epsilon_{eq,ini}^{compression}$) and 100 at tensile side ($\epsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile}$) in our previous study [1]. However, in Section 4.2, as the flexural deformation proceeds, damage occurred at the tensile side of the specimen from experimental observation. In the previous FE model ($\epsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile} = 100$), the damage at tensile side could not be represented. Differently, in this study, the damage initiation strain $\epsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile}$ at tensile side was identified from tensile test as represented in Section 4.1.

Once the damage initiation criteria were satisfied, further strain caused degradation of material stiffness coefficients as a function of the damage variable D . It was assumed that tape delamination at out-of-plane direction was damaged. Therefore, damage evolution curve was non-linear curve as the out-of-plane shear properties dominated by tape delamination. The damage evolution curve was shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Damage evolution curve.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Identification of damage initiation criteria from tensile test

The damage initiation strain $\varepsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile}$ was identified from tensile strain of 0.01 at fracture point as shown in Figure 2. At this time, plastic tensile strain ε_{11}^p was 3.3e-4. It was assumed that the tensile test was pure tension of 11-direction. In case of pure tension, the incremental plastic strains were defined by Equation (3) [5].

$$d\varepsilon_{11}^p : d\varepsilon_{22}^p : d\varepsilon_{33}^p = (G + H) : -H : -G \quad (3)$$

It was assumed that the shear strain increments were negligible. Equivalent plastic strain increment was defined by Equation (4) from equations (2) and (3).

$$d\varepsilon^p = \sqrt{\frac{F + G\left(\frac{H}{G+H}\right)^2 + H\left(\frac{G}{G+H}\right)^2}{FG + FH + GH}} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \quad (4)$$

Equivalent plastic strain was 3.3e-3 calculated from using Equation (4) and Table 2. Thus, the tensile damage initiation strain $\varepsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile}$ was identified as 3.3e-3. The damage initiation criteria are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Damage initiation criteria.

4.2 Experiment and simulation for three-point bending

Regarding the symmetry of the specimen, the FE analysis was performed on the quarter three-dimensional model as shown in Figure 9. Material directions of 1, 2 and 3 were corresponding x, y and z direction respectively. The flexural analysis was conducted using the damage initiation strain $\varepsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile}$ of 3.3e-3 identified from the tensile test. The experiment and simulation results of the flexural test are indicated in Figure 10. The results of the previous model with $\varepsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile} = 100$ are also shown in Figure 10 for evaluating the effect of $\varepsilon_{eq,ini}^{tensile}$. Until 0.010 of flexural strain, the difference between the results of the previous and the proposed models was not confirmed. More than this flexural strain, flexural stress did not decrease in the previous model. On the other hand, flexural stress was reduced in the proposed model. Figure 11 shows the damage distribution at flexural strain of 0.010, 0.015 and 0.020 obtained from the previous model and the proposed model for test specimen of 2, 4 and 6 mm in thickness. It can be seen that the simulation results from the proposed model are consistent with the experimental results. At 0.015 of flexural strain, it was found that damage occurs at the tensile side of the specimen in the proposed model. As the flexural deformation proceeds, the damaged region spreads through the thickness direction. Figure 12 shows flexural behavior images of test specimen with thickness of 4 and 6 mm. It is confirmed that damage occurs at tensile side of the specimen at

0.023 and 0.018 of flexural strain respectively. From comparison Figure 11 and Figure 12, it can be seen that the damage initiate predicted by the proposed model is consistent with the experimental results.

Figure 9: Three-point bending model of FE model.

Figure 10: Flexural stress-flexural strain curves obtained from experiment and FEM at (a) 2 mm, (b) 4 mm and (c) 6 mm of thickness.

Thickness	2 mm		4 mm		6 mm	
Flexural strain (-)	Previous model	Proposed model	Previous model	Proposed model	Previous model	Proposed model
0.010						
0.015						
0.020						

Figure 11: Distribution of damage variable from three-point bending FEM. (top) Legend and location.

Figure 12: Flexural behavior images at flexural strain of 0.010 and the strain of occurring damage on tensile side.

5 CONCLUSION

We proposed a simple constitutive FE model defining in-plane homogeneity, out-of-plane anisotropy, strain hardening and damage initiation/propagation without consideration of the shape of the tapes explicitly for CTT. In addition, we identified damage criteria to consider tensile damage from tensile test. As a result of validation of the proposed model at three-point bending FE analysis, the mechanical flexural behavior and distribution of damage agreed well with experimental results for a variety of specimen.

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